

paper Chain

Implementation of Circular Case 2
D5.7 - April (M47)

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WP5, Task 5.7

New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

Deliverable No.	5.7
Dissemination level	Public
Work Package	5. Real Scale Demonstration of the circular value chain
Task	5.2. Demo in Spain. PPI and transport infrastructure
Lead beneficiary	1. ACCIONA
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	UPC, TECNALIA
Due date of deliverable	30 April 2021
Actual submission date	13/05/2021

Document history

V	Date	Beneficiary	Author
1 st Draft	21/04/2021	UPC	Diego Aponte
2 nd Draft	28/04/2021	TECNALIA	Asier Oleaga
3 rd Draft	29/04/2021	ACCIONA	Juan José Cepriá, Roberto Orejana
Final	12/05/2021	ACCIONA	Juan José Cepriá

0. Executive summary

This report updates the status of the three pilots built during the first half of the project life. The constructive details and first results were detailed in deliverable 5.3.

The present report focuses in the monitoring data and their interpretation, covering the technical performance, structural integrity and environmental follow up.

Pilot 1 (S-EST2 layer in Ejea) has been regularly checked in order assess the structural integrity of this unpaved road by doing inspections of the surface regularity, bumps formation or fine flowing. The road has three piezometers installed cutting the road section with the aim of collecting leachates to be checked along this period.

Pilot 2 (S-EST3 layer in Villamayor) monitoring during the previous report has carried on during this stage increasing the available data. Road inspections have confirmed the excellent state of repair and the absence of any damage. New load plate test have been conducted in the same points tested during the quality control programme. The inspection was completed with lightweight deflectometer analysis, confirming the appropriate evolution of the field trial at a 3-year scenario. Along this period, a new soil and water sampling campaign of has been conducted in order to detect any potential increase in metals over the previous levels, with no measurable differences observed along this time.

Monitoring data of Pilot 3 (soil cement layer in a highway) is only compiled in this report, as there were no previous data available since the pilot construction was finished just before the due date of deliverable 5.3. The type of layer and location, encapsulated between sealing layers, conditions the type of monitoring. It has been based on onsite testing by means of falling weight deflectometre testing in both, the soil – ash and the standard soil – cement layer. Additionally, laboratory specimens were manufactured and tested to measure the compressive strength evolution. Finally, the environmental monitoring has been conducted at laboratory scale in order to measure the metal and salts mobility over time, given the impossibility of recovering any leachate on site. For the same reason, there were no sampling for environmental monitoring on site as discussed in deliverable 5.3.

In all the cases the leaching properties have been assessed by producing laboratory specimens with the soil, WPFA, cement and lime picked up during the pilot execution, reproducing the same placing conditions (dosing, dry density and moisture content). Complete leaching test has been performed at 7, 28, 90, 180 and 360 curing days, showing the metal mobility evolution and the differences and similarities with the standard binders. These tests have shown that the WPFA blended samples remained as inert soils except for those parameters that surpassed the threshold limit in the original soil (chlorides in S-EST2 and Sulphates in S-EST3). Antimony slightly overpassed the limit for inert waste in all the cases (WPFA and cement treated soils) despite the fact that this element is not found in relevant amounts in the WPFA or cement.

Keywords

Structural road integrity	State of repair	Deflectometre	Load plate test	Leaching
Compressive strength	Piezometre			

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Abbreviations and acronyms:

WPBA: Waste Paper Bottom Ash	GW: Groundwater
WPFA: Waste Paper Fly Ash	SW: Surficial Water
PPI: Pulp and Paper Industry	NGRs: Generic Levels of Reference
QA: Quality Assurance	VNGR: No Risk Generic Value
LA: Los Angeles Coefficient	VGI: Intervention Value
S-EST2: Type-2 Stabilised layer	CHE: Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro
S-EST3: Type-3 Stabilised layer	ICP: Ion Chromatography
Mpa: Megapascal	HPLC: High-performance liquid chromatography
FWD: Falling Weight Deflectometre	

1. Background

Spanish Circular Case 2 consists of 3 pilots covering the three main stabilised road layers recognised in the Spanish Road Regulation (PG3: S-EST2-type stabilised layer, S-EST3-type stabilised layer and Soil Cement layer). Lime (in S-EST2) and cement (in S-EST3 and Soil – cement layer) were fully replaced by Waste Paper Fly Ash. S-EST2 and S-EST3 pilots were built in October 2018 and soil cement pilot in October 2019.

The location details, technical requirements for these pilots, constructive pilot details, quality control results can be consulted in deliverable 5.3. First performance monitoring data covering 16 months for S-EST2 and S-EST3 and 5 months for Soil cement are also compiled in this deliverable.

Deliverable 5.3 described the technical performance monitoring results departing from the quality control recorded during the pilots' execution and thanks to sequential inspections to detect damages or damages of the stabilised layers reflected on the road surfaces. The main results were:

Technical performance:

S-EST2 layer was in perfect condition after almost two years in operation, with any damage detected and an excellent road surface, with no bumps, potholes or wheel impressions. As this pilot has a simple structure, with just 15 cm of graded aggregates on top of the stabilised layer, no additional monitoring was conducted during the previous period.

S-EST3 followed the same pattern. The field inspections did not detect damages associated with the performance of the stabilised layer. Some weak cracks appeared on the double bituminous surface dressing reflecting the shrinkage of the cement stretch because of its high rigidity (5.2 Mpa at 7 curing days). This cracking pattern did not appear on the WPFA stretch thanks to the slow compressive strength development. The only damages detected were located in the joint between the lanes in a curve near the end of the stretch. They consists of some pavement potholes, but not related with the WPFA-stabilised layer. All damages were repaired during the inspections.

In this case, an intense research was conducted in order to assess the potential swelling properties of WPFA in combination with a sulphate-rich soil, as it is the case of S-EST3 in Villamayor de Gállego. A certain swelling potential was identified due to the ettringite formation in a higher proportion than with the cement used for this stabilisation. This is due to the lower calcium content and high proportion of siliceous fly ashes of this type of cement. Anyway, no swelling was detected in the stabilised soil during this first monitoring stage.

The **soil cement** layer was executed and no further data was gathered in deliverable 5.3 apart from those collected during the quality control of the layer building. The

pilot demonstrated that all technical requirements were fulfilled. Extensive data on these results can be consulted in deliverable 5.3.

Environmental performance:

The environmental performance has been assessed in **S-EST2 and S-EST3** pilots during the first stage through:

- Sampling of soils along the roadsides of the stabilised layer and vegetation (leaves and vegetables) picked up in the road surroundings in order to measure the concentration of the main elements of concern. This sampling took place just before the pilot execution and after it ("pre" and "post" pilot construction campaigns). The same referenced points were sampled in order to assess the impact of the use of WPFA. The sampling campaign was designed according to a preliminary risk assessment.
- Sampling of surficial waters (upstream and downstream) before and after the pilot construction.
- Sampling of percolation waters (leachates) through the stabilised layers collected in three piezometres installed along the pilots. This sampling and analysis took place after every relevant rainfall event (scarce in this area).

The results showed that no significant variations were detected in the chemical composition of soils and waters before and after the pilot execution, so that, no relevant environmental impact, and therefore, potential unacceptable risks could be inferred from the construction stage.

The analysed waters had a chemical composition similar to those natural waters, although with a certain increase in some salts (sulphates), compatible with the effect of the surrounding soils.

The **soil cement** pilot did not include any onsite environmental monitoring since the preliminary environmental risk assessment as it was going to be completely encapsulated between asphalt layers, however, samples of soil, WPFA and cement were taken to produce laboratory specimens with the same conditions of dose rate, density and moisture content for serial leaching tests at laboratory scale.

This testing strategy for leaching evaluation were also repeated in the case of the other two pilots, S-EST2 and S-EST3. The preliminary results of these tests were not included in the former deliverable.

The present document covers the monitoring along the whole project life, providing updated data of the onsite monitoring that includes three years in the case of S-EST2 and S-EST3 pilots and two years in the case of the soil cement.

It is also compiled all laboratory data obtained with the specimens fabricated at the same field conditions in order to assess the mechanical and leaching properties and their evolution along time.

Finally, a new soil and water sampling campaign was conducted in order to assess the three-year scenario, as well as some new load plate test in the same locations

as in the quality control campaign, in order to evaluate the mechanical performance evolution in the case of S-ES2 and S-EST3 pilots.

For the soil cement layer, a Falling Weight Deflectometer (FWD) campaign was conducted two years after the pilot construction as onsite monitoring.

This deliverable compiles this update and concludes about the pilots 'performance.

TABLE 1: SUMMARY OF PILOTS' MONITORING ALONG THE PROJECT LIFE.

Type of monitoring	S-EST2		S-EST3		Soil Cement	
	1 year scenario	3 year scenario	1 year scenario	3 year scenario	Quality control	2 years scenario
Load plate tests	X	X	X	X	X	
Compressive Strength	X		X		X	X
FWD						X
Road integrity (visual inspections)	X	X	X	X		
Swell potential			X			
Leaching (lab scale)	X		X		X	
Percolation waters (from piezometers)	X	X	X	X		
Soil and vegetation chemistry	X	X	X	X		
Surficial waters			X	X		

2. Stabilised road layer type S-EST2

The present chapter covers the two aspects assessed: Technical and environmental performance. Moreover, these aspects includes onsite and laboratory monitoring data.

2.1. Technical performance monitoring

Five field inspections have been conducted along the 3 year-period monitoring. The last one was held on September 2020. Most of them have been done along with the Council technical staff who has emitted a certificate of compliance thanks to the good performance of the stretch.

The integrity of the surface graded aggregated layer has been found in perfect conditions with no bumps, potholes, cracks, heave or any deformation in general, thanks to the preserved rigidity of the subgrade stabilisation.

There is a striking contrast with the rest of the road that remains without subgrade stabilisation, which is full of irregularities and bumps despite the permanent conservation works.

FIGURE 1. Detail of the excellent finish of the road surface.

In order to evaluate the evolution of the layer rigidity, on September 2020 three load plate tests were carried out in the same points as they were conducted during the quality control of the field trial.

TABLE 2: LOAD PLATE TEST DATA EVOLUTION.

Location (mileage)	Binder	E_{v1}		E_{v2}		E_{v2}/E_{v1}	
		Oct 2018	Sept 2020	Oct 2018	Sept 2020	Oct 2018	Sept 2020
0+153	WPFA	150	99	293	281	2.0	2.9
0+453	WPFA	142	72	287	145	2.0	2.0
0+953	Lime	101	70	193	276	1.9	4.0

The data shows that WPFA rigidity seems to keep stable along time, although there are some data discrepancy. The only one data available for the lime stretch showed a relevant increase in the second load cycle.

The modulus ratio is sometimes higher than 2.2 as it is stated in the Spanish standard. This has been interpreted as a lack of accuracy due to the testing conditions. For this testing, the graded aggregate layer was removed in order to perform the load plate tests directly over the stabilised subgrade. This excavation (see figure number 2) could affect the first E_{v1} value, consequently, the E_{v2}/E_{v1} ratio.

FIGURE 2. PREPARING THE LOAD PLATE TESTS BY REMOVING THE GRADED AGGREGATE LAYER

2.2. Environmental monitoring. Field data.

TECNALIA established the environmental monitoring strategy for EJEA and carried out the sampling works, that consisted in the sampling of soils-sediments in referenced sampling points in curbs, groundwater from track wells and vegetation.

Soils: occasional run-off water may transport compounds (dissolved and particles) of concern from the pilot surface, core and side surfaces mainly to earth-based side parallel curbs so that, sediment. Six control points were selected based on previous referenced sampling points in 2018 (ECCUN-1, ECCUN-2, etc.). The aim was to check the potential impact in the same points due to run-off transportation. No other relevant transportation routes for compounds of concern in soils were considered in the 2021 study. Six curb soil-sediments samples were taken.

FIGURE 3. SOIL-SEDIMENT SAMPLING AT ECCUN-2 (EJEA). NOTICE THAT THE SOIL SAMPLE CONSISTED IN RENOVATED SEDIMENT CAUSED BY OCCASIONAL RUN-OFF ON CURB LINES.

Groundwater (GW): rainfall water infiltration can leach and transport pollutants to underground levels. For the pilot scenario located in EJEA, it was previously determined that no potential threat to groundwater could exist since, there is a shallow bedrock (< 2m) conforming a sealing thick layer underneath, and there is no relevant aquifer underneath. Nevertheless, it was considered worthy to sample the water infiltrated through the road section, captured by the wells installed along the road axis, in order to assess the potential leaching. This data could provide relevant information for replicability in other groundwater more sensible scenarios.

Two GW samples were taken (AG S-3, AG S-2), in 2 wells out of three installed in 2019. One of it (S-1) was not available due to bad conservation (damaged), and it was discarded to avoid poor representativeness.

FIGURE 4. GROUNDWATER SAMPLING IN S-3 WELL AT EJEA.

It should be noted that sampling infiltration water is difficult in this scenario due to the local dry climatology. Only sub-surface, occasional and isolated levels of GW and not connected are usually expected in the site. However, the optimal leachate sampling conditions emerged in late January 2021, thus the sampling campaign was carried out. In addition to the sampling, the physical-chemical parameters (pH and temperature) were measured in situ (Table 2). At the time of sampling, conductivity sensor was unavailable and thus, the measure was done later at lab.

TABLE 2. INFILTRATION WATER SAMPLING POINTS AT EJEA

Sampling Point (GW)	Sample	g.w.l.*	pH	Temp °C	Observ.	Date
S-2	AG-S2	0,72m	8,68	12,7°C	Turbid	27/01/2021
S-3	AG-S3	0,95m	8,39	11,8°C	turbid	27/01/2021

*groundwater level below surface

The sampling was done at a slow speed (<0,5 l/min), being the recovering rate of the groundwater quite poor, especially in S-3. Enough water was obtained to carry out the planned chemical analysis. Samples showed a very turbid aspect at the beginning of pumping (stabilization purge) and moved to a slight turbid aspect afterwards. No odour or pollutants (oil, etc.) were visually detected.

Vegetation: vegetation was sampled in two referenced points (EC-VEG3 and EC-VEG4), consisting on pine trees leaves samples. The aim was to assess any variation in the chemical charge of the leaves, caused mainly from dust generation by road

use and by chemical compounds adsorption through soil. Two vegetation samples were taken for their analysis (Figure 5).

FIGURE 5. VEGETATION (PINE TREE LEAVES) SAMPLING IN EC-VEG4 AT EJEA.

The inspection did not evidence any environmental damage or potential impact in the surrounding vegetation. The amount of dust deposited on the trees leaves was not relevant. The following map (Figure 6) shows the location of all the sampling points at EJEA.

FIGURE 6. SAMPLING POINTS LOCATION AT EJEA PILOT. 2021 SAMPLING POINTS ARE OUTLINED.

Results:

Soil-sediment, water and vegetation samples were analysed at the laboratory for the most environmentally significant compounds previously identified. Samples were analysed by TECNALIA (ENAC certified laboratory). The analytical set (table 3) applied was similar in all the samples, focusing in compounds of main concern selected from previous campaigns: heavy metals (Al, Pb, Sb, As, Ba, Be, Tl, V), chlorides, sulphides, pH, electrical conductivity (GW and SW).

Results were compared with those obtained at the same location in previous campaigns in 2018, and/or compared with regulatory references for the studied media, in order to determine the existence of any potential risk for human health and/or environment and to evaluate the need of a specific risk assessment.

TABLE 3. ANALYTICAL SET AND METHODOLOGY

Compound	Method	Media
Aluminium (Al), Antimony (Sb), Arsenic (As), Barium (Ba), Beryllium (Be), Lead (Pb), Thallium (Tl), Vanadium (V)	ICP-OES	SOILS-SEDIMENTS VEGETATION WATER
Chlorides	Ionic chromatography	
Sulphates		
Conductivity	Electrometric	
pH		

Table 4 shows all the results obtained for soils in 2021 and compared with available references for Regional (Aragón) soil quality and baseline, and the previous results obtained (pre and post monitoring campaigns) in 2018 (See Deliverable 5.3). Table 4 shows also the average increase of concentration for the period 2018-2021, and comparison between right side curb (ECCUN-1, ECCUN-3, ECCUN-5), and left side curb (ECCUN-2, ECCUN-4, ECCUN-6) points.

TABLE 4. SOIL. CONCENTRATIONS EVOLUTION FOR 2018-2021 PERIOD.

Compound	Increase avg. 2018 / 2021		
	Increase avg. 2018 / 2021	Increase avg. 2018 / 2021 Right curb	Increase avg. 2018 / 2021 Left curb
pH	12,59	11,83	13,34
Conductivity $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$	-33,15	-9,38	-56,92
Total contents mg/kg dry m.			
<i>Anions</i>			
Chlorides	-60,57	-39,85	-81,28
Sulphates	-92,69	n.a.	-92,69
<i>Metals</i>			
Aluminium (Al)	32,86	25,54	40,18
Antimony (Sb)	101,09	74,00	155,26
Arsenic (As)	23,89	24,50	23,28
Barium (Ba)	38,88	25,66	52,10
Beryllium (Be)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Lead (Pb)	1,31	8,19	-5,57
Thallium (Tl)	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.
Vanadium (V)	32,42	22,55	42,28

TABLE 5. ANALYTICAL RESULTS (SOILS) IN MG/KG- COMPARATIVE: NGRs AND BASELINE REF. Vs. 2018-2021 CAMPAIGNS.

Compound	VR90 en mg/kg	VR99 en mg/kg	Nivel F (INARSA - CSIC) en mg/kg	NGR ARAGÓN (IGME) en mg/kg			ECCUN-1A	ECCUN-1B	ECCUN-1 (27/01/21)	Increase (1A-1B)		ECCUN-2A	ECCUN-2B	ECCUN-2 (27/01/21)	Incremento (2A-2B)		Increase 2019 / 2021		
				Industrial	Urbano	Otros usos				%	%				%	%	%		
pH							8,4	8,5	8,3	1,19	-2,35	7,7	7,7	8,7	0,00	12,99			
Conductivity µs/cm							83	80	127	-3,61	58,75	1671	2180	133	30,46	-93,90			
Total contents mg/kg dry m.																			
Anions																			
Chlorides							54	71,8	<50	32,96	-30,36	5370	6830	157	27,19	-97,70			
Sulphates							<50	<50	<50	n.a.	n.a.	397	684	<50	72,29	-92,69			
Metals																			
Aluminium (Al)	8185	13920	31500	10000	10000	8185	5630	7010	12900	24,51	84,02	8980	25800	8470	187,31	-67,17			
Antimony (Sb)	3	6	1,8	300	30	3	<1	1,47	2,01	>47	36,73	<1	1,94	<2	>94	n.a.			
Arsenic (As)	26	45	24	260	26	26	2,46	3,28	4,32	33,33	31,71	3,77	7,2	4,16	90,98	-42,22			
Barium (Ba)	890	2635	188	10000	8900	890	52	46,5	80,8	-10,58	73,76	54,3	134	63,3	146,78	-52,76			
Beryllium (Be)	n.a	n.a	n.a	10	1	0,8	<0,8	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	<0,8	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.			
Lead (Pb)	36	64	18	270	270	45	7,8	6,8	7,39	-12,82	8,68	7,69	8,83	6,05	14,82	-31,48			
Thallium (Tl)	n.a	n.a	n.a	20	2	0,08	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.			
Vanadium (V)	100	195	n.a	10000	1000	100	16,1	14,2	23,5	-11,80	65,49	16,6	44,9	21,1	170,48	-53,01			

Compound	VR90 en mg/kg	VR99 en mg/kg	Nivel F (INARSA - CSIC) en mg/kg	NGR ARAGÓN (IGME) en mg/kg			ECCUN-3A	ECCUN-3B	ECCUN-3 (27/01/21)	Incremento (3A-3B)		ECCUN-4A	ECCUN-4B	ECCUN-4 (27/01/21)	Incremento (4A-4B)		Increase 2019 / 2021		
				Industrial	Urbano	Otros usos				%	%				%	%	%		
pH							7,4	6,9	8,3	-6,76	20,29	8,2	7,9	8,5	-3,66	7,59			
Conductivity µs/cm							222	265	164	19,37	-38,11	134	199	150	48,51	-24,62			
Total contents mg/kg dry m.																			
Anions																			
Chlorides							120	171	<50	42,50	-70,76	150	255	<50	70,00	-80,39			
Sulphates							<50	<50	<50	n.a.	n.a.	<50	<50	<50	n.a.	n.a.			
Metals																			
Aluminium (Al)	8185	13920	31500	10000	10000	8185	12200	24600	24900	101,64	1,22	10200	11000	34300	7,84	211,82			
Antimony (Sb)	3	6	1,8	300	30	3	1,25	1,51	3,19	20,80	113,26	<1	1,52	3,88	>52	155,26			
Arsenic (As)	26	45	24	260	26	26	6,11	5,17	7,18	-15,38	38,88	4,21	4,28	9,25	1,66	116,12			
Barium (Ba)	890	2635	188	10000	8900	890	63,2	106	113	67,72	6,60	56,5	55,2	158	-2,30	186,23			
Beryllium (Be)	n.a	n.a	n.a	10	1	0,8	<0,8	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	<0,8	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.			
Lead (Pb)	36	64	18	270	270	45	10,5	8,83	11,2	-15,90	26,84	9,56	9,52	11,7	-0,42	22,90			
Thallium (Tl)	n.a	n.a	n.a	20	2	0,08	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.			
Vanadium (V)	100	195	n.a	10000	1000	100	21,6	37,1	39,2	71,76	5,66	16,8	18,4	54,3	9,52	195,11			

Compound	VR90 en mg/kg	VR99 en mg/kg	Nivel F (INARSA - CSIC) en mg/kg	NGR ARAGÓN (IGME) en mg/kg			ECCUN-5A	ECCUN-5B	ECCUN-5 (27/01/2021)	Incremento (5A-5B)		ECCUN-6A	ECCUN-6B	ECCUN-6 (27/01/21)	Incremento (6A-6B)		Increase 2019 / 2021		
				Industrial	Urbano	Otros usos				%	%				%	%	%		
pH							7,7	7,4	8,7	-3,90	17,57	7,1	7,2	8,6	1,41	19,44			
Conductivity µs/cm							132	162	83	22,73	-48,77	202	222	106	9,90	-52,25			
Total contents mg/kg dry m.																			
Anions																			
Chlorides							74	61,3	<50	-17,16	-18,43	117	146	<50	24,79	-65,75			
Sulphates							<50	<50	<50	n.a.	n.a.	<50	<50	<50	n.a.	n.a.			
Metals																			
Aluminium (Al)	8185	13920	31500	10000	10000	8185	9390	19900	12700	48,03	-8,63	17700	19900	15100	12,43	-24,12			
Antimony (Sb)	3	6	1,8	300	30	3	<1	1,36	<2	>36	n.a.	1,35	1,59	<2	-17,78	n.a.			
Arsenic (As)	26	45	24	260	26	26	5,47	4,82	4,96	-11,88	2,90	7,3	6,17	5,92	-15,48	-4,05			
Barium (Ba)	890	2635	188	10000	8900	890	56,7	68,1	65,8	20,11	-3,38	75,5	73,6	90,4	-2,52	22,83			
Beryllium (Be)	n.a	n.a	n.a	10	1	0,8	<0,8	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	0,85	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.			
Lead (Pb)	36	64	18	270	270	45	8,36	8,13	7,24	-2,75	-10,95	9,81	9,35	8,59	-4,69	-8,13			
Thallium (Tl)	n.a	n.a	n.a	20	2	0,08	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.			
Vanadium (V)	100	195	n.a	10000	1000	100	16,9	22,9	22,1	35,50	-3,49	31,5	30,8	26,1	-2,22	-15,26			

New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

From the soil analysis compiled in tables 4 and 5 the following observations can be set:

- Substantial decrease (80-90%) in salts (chlorides and sulfates) was observed between 2018-2021. This can be related to their highly soluble nature and run-off mechanisms.
- All the heavy metals, except Be, Th and Pb, increased clearly their concentrations in the soils after ≈2,5 years, ranging from +20% to more than 100% in the case of Antimony (Sb).
- Concentrations in soils after 2,5 years were below the references for soil quality for the applicable pilot construction (urban-industrial).
- Exceptionally, Aluminum (Al) increase exceeds in one sample (ECCUN-4 2021) the reference NGR level, with a peak of 34300mg/kg, which is slightly higher than the baseline (INARSA 31.500mg/kg).
- Left and right curbs show different increase rates. In general, left curb soil-sediment samples (ECCUN-2, ECCUN-4, and ECCUN-6) show higher increases for the heavy metals and a larger decrease for salts (chlorides) for the period 2018-2021. This can be indicative of a bigger run-off flow (visual inspection confirmed-new and prominent sedimentary formations), and therefore, compounds mobilisation and post sedimentation in the left curb rather than in the right one.

Evaluation:

- Compounds seem to behave differently regarding mobilisation: heavy metals show an increase of their concentrations, while anions such as chlorides and sulphates decrease notably. This could be explained, as a hypothesis, due to their different behavior and solubility rates, where anions could be prone to be transported by run-off further distances due to their highest solubility, meanwhile heavy metals to be concentrated in the sediment particles in a shorter path.
- Concentrations of compounds of concern do not exceed the GLR levels (potential risk related levels for soils in Aragón), and site use (urban-industrial). Therefore, no additional risk assessment for human health and/or environment is needed.
- The exception to the previous fact is the Aluminum (Al) compound, which is higher in concentration for a single sample (ECCUN-4), than the NGRs, but concentrations are close to a natural baseline (according to INARSA study). It must be noticed that according to previous considerations -explained in this project (D5.3)-, the site is naturally very rich (baseline) in Aluminum. Therefore, the concentrations of Al observed should not be considered as an environmental threat.

Groundwater (GW)

Table 6 shows all the analytical results (in µg/L) obtained for GW sampling in 2021, and their comparison with several reference values such as CHE VNGR (No risk) and VGI (Intervention) values¹ and CHE adopted Groundwater Directive 2016 values and CHE additional values for endangered groundwater masses. There is no previous Gw

¹ Niveles Genéricos de Referencia (NGR); aguas de la cuenca del Ebro (CHE).

reference samples for comparative purposes, since wells were dry at previous campaigns.

TABLE 6. ANALYTICAL RESULTS IN $\mu\text{G/L}$ (GW). COMPARATIVE WITH REFERENCE VALUES.

Compound	VNGR ¹ ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	VGI ² ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Threshold limit Directive 2006/118/EC (CHE) ³ ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	Threshold limit Endangered waters (CHE) ⁴ ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	AG-S2 (2021) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)	AG-S3 (2021) ($\mu\text{g/L}$)
Heavy metals						
Aluminium (Al)	-	-	-	200	450	34
Antimony (Sb)	80	280	-	-	<1	1,2
Arsenic (As)	50	70	10	-	1,5	<1
Barium (Ba)	-	-	-	-	59	46
Beryllium (Be)	-	-	-	-	<20	<20
Lead (Pb)	-	-	10	-	<5	<5
Thallium (Tl)	-	-	-	-	<10	<10
Vanadium (V)	-	-	-	-	<20	<20
Anions						
Chlorides	-	-	10-8737 mg/L	-	440 mg/L	397 mg/L
Sulphates	-	-	27-4340 mg/L	-	35,6 mg/L	41 mg/L
Physical-chemical						
Conductivity (20°C)	-	-	388- 18919 $\mu\text{S/cm}$	-	1483 $\mu\text{S/cm}$	1420 $\mu\text{S/cm}$

(1) VNGR – “Valor genérico de no riesgo (VNGR)” (No Risk Generic Value).

(2) VGI – “Valor genérico de intervención (VGI)” (Intervention Value)

(3) Reference DIRECTIVE 2006/118/EC for groundwater. Applicable to 71 endangered water masses.

(4) CHE reference values for endangered aquifers. Additional values to (4).

From the analysis of Table 6 the following observations were done for groundwater:

- GW values for heavy metals were under the CHE VNGR (Risk) and VGI (Intervention values) for Sb and As.
- Aluminum (Al) value was over the “Valor Umbral Directive” 2006/118/EC (CHE) in one of the sample (AG-S2).
- Chlorides and Sulphates showed not remarkable values according to the DIRECTIVE defined ranges.

Evaluation:

- References for compounds of environmental significance were not surpassed, but exceptionally in the case of Aluminum (Al). This value was compared, as a conservative exercise, with the CHE value for endangered waters, scenario that in fact does not apply to the pilot site (no real aquifer existence underneath the pilot). **No relevant impact to groundwater by pilot construction is foreseen.** It must be considered that the site soils nature are rich in Aluminium (Al). For replicability purposes more studies in other scenarios regarding to this compound should be done in order to assess the real impact originated by the binder.

Vegetation

Table 7 shows the results obtained, whereas in Table 8, compares these results with the samples taken at the same points in the previous sampling campaigns (2018), as well as the increase (in %).

TABLE 7. ANALYTICAL RESULTS OF VEGETATION SAMPLES AT EJEА.

Compound (mg/kg)	ECVEG-3 (2021)	ECVEG-4 (2021)
pH	6,6	7,6
Conductivity $\mu\text{s/cm}$	1124	542
Total contents mg/kg dry m.		
<i>Anions</i>		
Chlorides	<50	<50
Sulphates	<50	209
<i>Metals</i>		
Aluminum (Al)	618	318
Antimony (Sb)	<2	<2
Arsenic (As)	<2	<2
Barium (Ba)	17,1	14,9
Beryllium (Be)	<2	<2
Lead (Pb)	<2	<2
Thallium (Tl)	<2	<2
Vanadium (V)	<2	<2

TABLE 8. ANALYTICAL RESULTS (VEGETATION) AND COMPARATIVE (2018-2021). EJEА.

Compound	ECVEG-3A	ECVEG-3B	ECVEG-3 (2021)	Increase (2018-2021)		ECVEG-4A	ECVEG-4B	ECVEG-4 (2021)	Incremento (4A-4B)		Increase (2018-2021)
				Increase (3A-3B)	%				Incremento (4A-4B)	%	
pH	5,2	7	6,6	34,62	-5,71	6,3	6,6	7,6	4,76	15,15	
Conductivity $\mu\text{s/cm}$	1111	1018	1124	-8,37	10,41	987	1470	542	48,94	-63,13	
Total contents mg/kg dry m.											
<i>Anions</i>											
Chlorides	287	362	<50	26,13	-86,19	641	916	<50	42,90	-94,54	
Sulphates	314	226	<50	-28,03	-77,88	148	236	209	59,46	-11,44	
<i>Metals</i>											
Aluminum (Al)	750	1290	618	72,00	-52,09	523	1150	318	119,89	-72,35	
Antimony (Sb)	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	<1	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	
Arsenic (As)	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	
Barium (Ba)	8,48	10,9	17,1	28,54	56,88	7,43	9,5	14,9	27,86	56,84	
Beryllium (Be)	<0,8	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	<0,8	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	
Lead (Pb)	7,67	7,73	<2	0,78	-74,13	11,1	43,2	<2	289,19	-95,37	
Thallium (Tl)	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	<1	<1	<2	n.a.	n.a.	
Vanadium (V)	<1	2,55	<2	155,00	-21,57	<1	2,54	<2	154,00	-21,26	

From the analysis of Table 8 the following observations were done for Vegetation:

- Decrease in all the compounds of interest, especially on chlorides and sulphates (no detected), except for Barium (Ba).
- Barium (Ba) increases an average of 56% from 2018. It must be noticed that Barium levels in the soils are far below reference values in the site.

Evaluation:

- Field inspection did not show any visually remarkable damage or any other relevant issues close to the pilot surrounding vegetation.

Notable decrease of most of the compounds of concern after the 2,5 years monitoring period. **No potential risk for vegetation is foreseen.**

2.3. Environmental monitoring. Laboratory data

Objective

The objective of compliance leaching test is to evaluate the effect of stabilized soil with WPFA at different ages on the release of elements of concern using the leaching technique.

Material and methods

The leaching test is carried out according to EN-12457-2 (Compliance test for leaching of granular waste materials and sludges). Then the results are compared according to European Union Council (1999/31/EC) for considering the material as inert or non-hazardous.

The liquid to solid ratio was considered 10 l/kg and a particle size of at least 95% less than 4mm. The material is brought in contact with water and agitated for 24 hours.

Test specimens of 100 * 60 mm are manufactured with soil + 3 %wt WPFA to determine the leaching behaviour. Two samples with soil-WPFA are made for each age (7d, 30d, 60d, 180, 360 days). Additionally, control samples were made by only soil for each date.

After manufacturing the samples, they are left to cure for designated ages. When the curing is finished, they are dried at 40 °C for 24 hours. After drying, due to EN 12457-2 standard requires samples with particle sizes less than 4mm, they are ground until 95% of the material passes through 4mm sieve.

On the sieved material, the leaching test is carried out using a particular liquid to solid ratio of 10 l/kg of dry matter. After 24 hours, the material is filtered and, on the eluate, chemical analysis like pH, conductivity, high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) and ion chromatography (ICP) is carried out.

Results

The soil released fluoride concentrations at different curing ages higher than the inert waste limit (Figure 7), although as it can be seen in the graph, the natural soil releases even higher concentrations of fluorides so that, WPFA is not the origin of fluoride leaching. Similarly, the soil released high amount of chloride due to its nature, and stabilizing it with WPFA led to higher concentration of chloride in the mix (Figure 8) surpassing the limit for inert waste. Sulfate (Figure 9) values are below the inert waste for all ages; however, care should be taken out due to high concentration of sulphate and formation ettringite, which is an expansion reaction.

FIGURE 7: FLUORIDE RELEASE OF SOIL AND STABILIZED SOIL WITH 3% WPFA.

FIGURE 8: CHLORIDE RELEASE OF SOIL AND STABILIZED SOIL WITH 3% WPFA.

FIGURE 9: SULFATE RELEASE OF SOIL AND STABILIZED SOIL WITH 3% WPFA.

The heavy metals release from soil are below the limit values for inert waste as shown in Figure 10, only antimony (Sb) surpasses the inert waste limit after stabilization, for all curing ages as shown in Figure 11, whereas other metal's leaching decreases significantly, such as Lead (Pb).

FIGURE 10: HEAVY METAL RELEASE FROM ORIGINAL SOIL (TESTED AT THE SAME AGES AS STABILIZED SOIL).

FIGURE 11: HEAVY METAL RELEASE FROM STABILIZED SOIL WITH 3%WT WPFA FOR DIFFERENT AGING.

Conclusion

The leaching tests for WPFA-stabilised soil have been carried out to determine the potential release of elements of concern under a standardized method. The results showed that soil stabilization with WPFA surpasses the threshold limit in chlorides due to the high chloride concentration in the natural soils.

The case of antimony is slightly different. Despite the low Sb concentration in WPFA or in soil, the mobility increases in the WPFA stabilised layer probably because of the pH increase (usually from slightly over 9 to 12,7). In any case, leaching values are clearly within the Non-Hazardous limit for Sb.

3. Stabilised road layer type S-EST3

3.1. Technical performance. Field data

This pilot has a higher complexity as it is paved. The pavement is a simple double dressing, very sensible to any deformation of the subbase/subgrade, which facilitates the detection of any malfunction of the stabilised layer.

Six visual inspections have been carried out since the pilot construction. The inspections were focused on any potential deformation related to heave in the upper area with an underlying soil consisting of silty gypsum and to pavement settlements due to an excess of settlement or even collapse of the stabilised layer along the whole alignment.

The inspections revealed the following information:

- Some potholes appeared in two different areas due to slipping between the dressing layers and along the junction of the stabilised layer in a road curve. These minor failures are not related with the stabilisation itself. All defects were repaired on January 2020 and have not appeared again.
- The cement stretch showed an incipient cracking pattern consisting of transversal cracks separated each 3 to 5 m. This cracking is a consequence of the high rigidity reached by the cement-stabilised layer. S-EST3 layers do not foresee pre-cracking to avoid transversal pave cracking as it is foreseen for soil – cement layers. The reason is that the technical requirement for S-EST3 layers is 1,5 Mpa of Uniaxial Compressive Strength (UCS) in comparison with 2,5 – 4,5 Mpa for soil cement layers. In this sense, WPFA has showed a clear advantage to prevent paving from transversal cracking because it develops its strength over the medium term while cement increases rigidity very sharply. A slow reaction provides more time for stress dissipation.

Additionally, three load plate tests were carried out in the same points as done during the quality control tests. The following table summarises the parameters:

TABLE 9. LOAD PLATE TEST DATA EVOLUTION.

Location (mileage)	Binder	E_{v1}		E_{v2}		E_{v2}/E_{v1}	
		Oct 2018	Sept 2020	Oct 2018	Sept 2020	Oct 2018	Sept 2020
0 + 450	WPFA	218	54	397	321	1.8	6
0 + 750	WPFA	76	116	276	466	3.6	4
0 + 950	Cement	193	205	1500	711	7.8	5

FIGURE 12: EDGE INTEGRITY ON JANUARY 2020 (LEFT). DETAIL OF ONE OF THE CRACKS APPEARED IN THE CEMENT CONTROL STABILISED LAYER (RIGHT).

3.2. Technical performance. Laboratory data

The objective is to carry out a deep characterization of material used in the experimental section, as well as to determine the evolution of the resistance of the stabilized soil and its durability in the presence of sulphates along 2 years of testing. Furthermore, its environmental aspects also studied and compared to those with cement samples.

The soil and waste paper fly ash (WPFA) are delivered in October 2018 from the field trial that was carried out in Zaragoza, Spain, to the laboratory services at Polytechnic University of Catalonia (UPC). In addition, a cement type IV is delivered in February 2019. In addition to soil and WPFA, a subgrade soil was also delivered for this study.

The aspects covered in this laboratory analysis of performance are:

- Durability analysis due to sulfate attack. This is due to having a large amount of gypsum and this may affect the upper stabilized soil layer (with WPFA or cement) (if the subgrade layer becomes in contact with groundwater and due to capillary action in subgrade soil, the water may reach the stabilized soil and causes swelling).
- Compressive Strength development

3.2.1. Durability analysis

One of the common problems in some binders that can affect the durability of a stabilized soil is being exposed to a sulphate source (sulphate attack). This source can come from rain from surface of the pavement, or from ground water if the below soil is rich in sulphate (due to existence of capillary action in soil). It occurs when tri-calcium phase inside the binder (It can be Portland cement or any cementitious material), becomes in contact with water containing sulphate. The presence of calcium oxide and aluminium

oxide in the binder react with sulphate and water solution and leads to expansion. This could happen in WPFA due to having almost similar properties to cement. To study durability effect, samples were made to measure the displacement in horizontal axle in a confined system using PVC moulds with the following conditions:

The conditions of this test are as follows:

- The measurement is taking place on the first day of fabrication, and then once a week.
- Three different water is being used to simulate different scenarios. First water is tap water (normal water).
- The second water contains 2.5 g/L sulfate. Samples made with water 2 contain subgrade soil. This is due to the subgrade soil contains large amount of sulfate and to avoid any dilution from subgrade soil to the water bath, 2.5 g/L sulfate is added to the water (the content of the sulfate in subgrade soil is determined using high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)).
- The third water has 20 g/L sulfate in order to accelerate the reactions inside the samples and to measure the swelling.
- The samples are placed inside the water bath for 1 day and left to dry for 6 day.
- Samples are made at two different temperatures (5°C and 20°C) (The temperature may affect the formation of new mineralogical compounds that may cause swelling in samples).
- To compare result, samples are made with cement too.

FIGURE 13: HORIZONTALLY CONFINED TEST FOR DIFFERENT WATER TYPE.

Moreover, samples are made with exactly same conditions as mentioned before with cement to compare the results (3% cement, density 2050 Kg/m³ with no delay time. Considered water: 7%).

TABLE 10: DURABILITY PVC SAMPLES PROPERTIES.

Sample Id	Samples	Condition	Storage condition
P1 S+WPFA P2 S+WPFA P3 S+WPFA P4 S+WPFA	Soil with 5% FA, delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to normal water for a day, and 6 day of drying	20 °C – 95% humidity
P5 S+WPFA P6 S+WPFA P7 S+WPFA P8 S+WPFA	Soil with 5% FA, delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to normal water for a day, and 6 day of drying	5 °C - Dry
P9 Sg+S+WPFA P10 Sg+S+WPFA P11 Sg+S+WPFA P12 Sg+S+WPFA	A layer of subgrade soil + Soil with 5% FA, delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to water with 2.5 g/l sulphate for a day, and 6 day of drying	20 °C – 95% humidity
P13 Sg+S+WPFA P14 Sg+S+WPFA P15 Sg+S+WPFA P16 Sg+S+WPFA	A layer of subgrade soil + Soil with 5% FA, delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to water with 2.5 g/l sulphate for a day, and 6 day of drying	5 °C - Dry
P17 S+WPFA P18 S+WPFA P19 S+WPFA P20 S+WPFA	Soil with 5% FA, delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to water with 20 g/l sulphate for a day, and 6 day of drying	20 °C – 95% humidity
P21 S+WPFA	Soil with 5% FA, delay time applied,	Being exposed to water with 20 g/l	5 °C - Dry

P22 S+WPFA P23 S+WPFA P24 S+WPFA	cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	sulphate for a day, and 6 day of drying	
P25 S+C P26 S+C	Soil with 3% cement, no delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to normal water for a day, and 6 day of drying	20 ° C – 95% humidity
P27 S+C P28 S+C	Soil with 3% cement, no delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to normal water for a day, and 6 day of drying	5 ° C - Dry
P29 S+C P30 S+C	Soil with 3% cement, no delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to water with 20 g/l sulphate for a day, and 6 day of drying	20 ° C – 95% humidity
P29 S+C P30 S+C	Soil with 3% cement, no delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to water with 20 g/l sulphate for a day, and 6 day of drying	5 ° C - Dry
P31 Sg+S+C P32 Sg+S+C	A layer of subgrade soil + Soil with 3% cement, no delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to water with 2.5 g/l sulphate for a day, and 6 day of drying	20 ° C – 95% humidity
P31 Sg+S+C P32 Sg+S+C	A layer of subgrade soil + Soil with 3% cement, no delay time applied, cured for 7 days in humidity chamber	Being exposed to water with 2.5 g/l sulphate for a day, and 6 day of drying	5 ° C - Dry

C: Cement, WPFA: Waste Paper Fly ash, S: Soil, Sg: Subgrade soil

To study the volumetric changes, another group of samples were fabricated as follows:

The standard EN 13286-49 is indicating for a cohesive soil or a soil that has enough fine particle size so that the experiment can carry out. Additionally, it is indicating to use only the fine portion of the soil (smaller than 6.3 mm) which in this soil most of the is higher than 6.3mm. Hence, to see the effect of the all particle, the volumetric test is carried out.

To carry out the experiment, representative soil is mixed with 5% WPFA and 8.2% of water. The 30 minutes delay time is applied and then the mixture is poured into the metallic mould (152 * 172mm) and compacted in four layers (each layer 20~30 seconds with vibrocompactor) until reaching the proctor density (2000 kg/m³).

After manufacturing the samples, they are placed inside an elastic membrane as shown in Figure 14. To have a reference for measuring and able to measure the swelling, eight metallic points were glued on the specimen, on the elastic membrane. Since the measurement point cannot glue to the soil specimen directly, they were glued to the elastic membrane instead. Four of the eight points were glued on top, and other four on the bottom. The first measurement is done immediately after fabricating the specimen.

FIGURE 14: EXPANSION SAMPLE WITH ELASTIC MEMBRANE.

Table 11 shows the detail of each samples for volumetric measurement with their conditions.

TABLE 11: VOLUMETRIC SAMPLES AND CONDITIONS.

Sample Id	Material	Condition	Water condition
M1	Soil + FA	5°C humidity chamber	Water 1
M2	Soil + FA	5°C humidity chamber	Water 1
M3	Soil + FA	5°C humidity chamber	Water 3

M4	Soil + FA	5°C humidity chamber	Water 3
M5	Soil + FA	20°C humidity chamber	Water 1
M6	Soil + FA	20°C humidity chamber	Water 1
M7	Soil + FA	20°C humidity chamber	Water 3
M8	Soil + FA	20°C humidity chamber	Water 3
M9	Soil + Cement	5°C humidity chamber	Water 1
M10	Soil + Cement	5°C humidity chamber	Water 1
M11	Soil + Cement	5°C humidity chamber	Water 3
M12	Soil + Cement	5°C humidity chamber	Water 3
M13	Soil + Cement	20°C humidity chamber	Water 1
M14	Soil + Cement	20°C humidity chamber	Water 1
M15	Soil + Cement	20°C humidity chamber	Water 3
M16	Soil + Cement	20°C humidity chamber	Water 3
M17	Sg + Soil + FA	5°C humidity chamber	Water2
M18	Sg + Soil + FA	5°C humidity chamber	Water2
M19	Sg + Soil + FA	20°C humidity chamber	Water2
M20	Sg + Soil + FA	20°C humidity chamber	Water2
M21	Sg + Soil + Cement	5°C humidity chamber	Water2
M22	Sg + Soil + Cement	5°C humidity chamber	Water2
M23	Sg + Soil + Cement	20°C humidity chamber	Water2
M24	Sg + Soil + Cement	20°C humidity chamber	Water2

Results.

Horizontally confined tests

In the following figures, confined swelling/shrinkage results and the evolution of the weight of the test specimens are shown after 700 days.

FIGURE 15. WEIGHT AND DISPLACEMENT, SOIL+FA+NORMAL WATER (20°C). P1, P2, P5, P6.

FIGURE 16. WEIGHT AND DISPLACEMENT, SOIL + CEMENT + NORMAL WATER (20°C) P25, P26.

The soil-WPFA and soil-cement at 20°C with the normal water are shown. It was observed a shrinkage of these samples. The maximum shrinkage value is 0.28%.

FIGURE 17. WEIGHT AND DISPLACEMENT EVOLUTION, SOIL+FA+NORMAL WATER (5°C) TEST SPECIMENS (P3,P4,P7,P8).

FIGURE 18. WEIGHT AND DISPLACEMENT, SOIL + CEMENT + NORMAL WATER (5°C). P27, P28.

The samples at 5°C for both WPA and cement have shown no significant swelling.

FIG. 19. WEIGHT/DISPLACEMENT, SOIL+SUB.+FA+2.5 G/L SO₄ WATER- 20°C. P9,P10,P11,P12.

FIGURE 20. WEIGHT AND DISPLACEMENT EVOLUTION, SOIL+SUBGRADE+CEMENT+2.5G/LITRE SO₄ WATER (20°C) TEST SPECIMENS (P33, P36).

FIGURE 21. WEIGHT/DISPLACEMENT, SOIL+SUBGR.+FA+2.5 G/LITRE SO₄ WATER (5°C). P13-16

FIGURE 22. WEIGHT AND DISPLACEMENT, SOIL+SUBGRADE+CEMENT+2.5G/LITRE SO4 (5°C) TEST SPECIMENS (P34, P35).

The samples containing subgrade soil both for WPFA and cement at different temperatures have not shown a significant swelling, although the weight is increased showing the absorption of water.

FIGURE 23. WEIGHT AND DISPLACEMENT, SOIL+FA+20 G/LITRE SO₄ WATER (20°C). P17,P18,P19,P20.

FIG. 24. WEIGHT/DISPLACEMENT, SOIL+FA+20 G/LITRE SO₄ WATER (5°C). P21,P22,P23,P24.

FIGURE 25. WEIGHT/DISPLACEMENT, SOIL+CEMENT+20 G/LITRE SO₄ WATER (20°C). P29, P30

FIGURE 26. WEIGHT AND DISPLACEMENT EVOLUTION, SOIL+CEMENT+20 G/LITRE SO4 WATER (5°C) TEST SPECIMENS (P31, P32).

The maximum measured shrinkage was about 0.36 % after 770 days.

Volumetric expansion (unconfined expansion)

The following figures represent the volumetric changes of the specimens for different conditions.

FIGURE 27: SOIL +WPFA @ 5°C - WATER 1 (M1, M2)

FIGURE 28: SOIL + WPFA @ 5°C – WATER 3 (M3, M4)

FIGURE 29: SOIL + WPFA @ 20°C – WATER 1 (M5, M6)

FIGURE 30: SOIL +WPFA @ 20°C – WATER 3 (M7, M8)

FIGURE 31: SOIL +CEMENT @ 5°C – WATER 1 (M9, M10)

FIGURE 32: SOIL +CEMENT @ 5°C – WATER 3 (M11, M12)

FIGURE 33: SOIL +CEMENT @ 20°C – WATER 1 (M13, M14)

FIGURE 34: SOIL + CEMENT @ 20°C – WATER 3 (M15, M16)

FIGURE 35: SUBGRADE SOIL + SOIL + WPFA @ 5°C – WATER 2 (M17, M18)

FIGURE 36: SUBGRADE SOIL + SOIL + WPFA @ 20°C – WATER 2 (M19, M20)

FIGURE 37: SUBGRADE SOIL + SOIL + CEMENT @ 5°C – WATER 2 (M21, M22)

FIGURE 38: SUBGRADE SOIL + SOIL + CEMENT @ 20°C – WATER 2 (M23, M24)

After 160 days, the experiment was cancelled due to appearance of mould on the samples (Figure 39).

The volumetric changes showed an expansion in the first 25 days, however after this date, tended shrink. With obtained results, the expansion is observed less than 2%.

FIGURE 39: PRESENCE OF MOULD ON SAMPLES, AT 5°C (LEFT) AND 20°C (RIGHT).

3.2.2. Strength development analysis

The strength gains in cement depends on its type and curing time. Typically, curing times are 1 day (for high early strength cement), 3 days, 7 days, 28 days and 90 days (for low heat of hydration cement). Since WPFA has showed some cementitious properties, the study of its strength over time becomes necessary.

To study the strength evolution of WPFA, samples are made for different ages (7d, 30d, 60d, 180d, and 360d). For each time, four samples were made. Additionally, to compare the result and have a reference point, compressive strength samples are made with cement (four for each time).

The soil-WPFA and soil-cement samples are made using standard EN 13285-41 for compressive strength for S-EST3 soil type in situ. However, instead of carrying out the experiment at 7 days, the samples are cured in a chamber room with 95% humidity at 20°C at different ages that are mentioned before.

For soil-WPFA samples, 5% WPFA is used. In addition, a delay time of 30 minutes is applied to slake the WPFA. The goal is to reach the density of 2000 Kg/m³. The optimum water is considered 8.2%. This value is obtained from field trial.

On the other hand, for soil-cement samples, the cement type, which was considered, is Cement (CEM IV/B (Q) 32.5N). 3% cement is used (the minimum allowance value for a soil E-EST3 according to PG-3). No delay time is applied for soil-cement samples. The optimum water is considered 7% (due to not being as porous as WPFA, the water amount is decreased). The density is 2050 Kg/m³.

The compressive strength for specimens is carried out for 7, 28, 60, 180 and 360 days. At 7-day age, the soil-WPFA and soil-cement obtained nearly the same strength, which both fulfilled the PG-3 requirement that is 1.5MPa at 7 days as shown in Figure 40.

However, the curing did not show any effect on soil-WPFA specimens and they reached the same strength as the 7 days (slightly improvement but not significant). On the other hand, soil-cement specimens obtained better strength by curing at which by the age of 360 days, the strength has been increased significantly over the 7 days.

FIGURE 40: COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH AT DIFFERENT AGES.

3.3. Environmental monitoring. Field data

The VILLAMAYOR pilot (S-EST3 layer) monitoring plan established by TECNALIA, was focused on the potential impact on both groundwater (gw) and surface water (sw), as most sensitive receptors and pollutants transportation ways. Soil monitoring sampling was discarded for this 2021 campaign due to the absence of impacts on the soil, detected in the previous campaigns. In addition, vegetation monitoring by sampling was discarded too, since none of the crops-vegetables sampled in previous campaigns were available at the time of sampling (wintertime) for comparison purposes. It must be noticed that no relevant impact related to the pilot was detected on vegetation from the previous campaigns.

Groundwater (GW): the strategy intended to sample the water contained in the dedicated monitoring wells (VG-P1, VG-P2, VG-P3). Nevertheless, at the time of sampling (2021) it was not possible to obtain any gw for different reasons (Table 3), due to no detection of water level, and bad well conservation – breakage in some case (Figure 41). In a sampling attempt on 2020, it was possible to obtain samples in two wells. It was concluded that there is not a continuous sub-superficial continuous water level at the depth of the wells (from 2 to 10 m.b.g). Groundwater level was observed only during few inspections to the site and after important rainfall events. These events were occasional and temporary GW disappeared quickly, representing an issue for the sampling strategy.

FIGURE 41. DAMAGED GROUNDWATER SAMPLING WELL IN VG P-3.

TABLE 12. GW SAMPLING POINTS AT VILLAMAYOR

Sampling Point (GW)	Sample	g.w.l.*	pH	Temp °C	Observations	Date
VG-P1	AG-P1	-	-	-	Dry	27/01/2021
VG-P2	AG-P2	-	-	-	Dry	27/01/2021
VG-P3	AG-P3	-	-	-	Dry	27/01/2021

*groundwater level below surface

Surface (SW): Surface water was sampled in the 2021 campaign: two irrigation canals (irrigation ditches) called “Canal irrigation ditch” and “Fafonda irrigation ditch” were

targeted (Table 13). Four SW samples were obtained upwards and downwards of the crossing points of the pilot road with the irrigation ditches (Figure 42). Before and during the Pilot construction event (2018), these watercourses were not operational, due to several other public works on the site that required their temporary closure. There is only a previous (2020) sample reference (AC-1) available for comparative purposes. In the latest campaign (2021), water flows ranged between $\approx 3\text{-}5$ l/s (visual approach).

TABLE 13. SW SAMPLING POINTS AT VILLAMAYOR

Sampling Point (sW)	pH	Temp °C	Location	Observations	Date
AC-1	8,69	11,2	Fafonda irrigation ditch - downwards	Clear water Organic/ faecal odour. Foamish	27/01/2021
AC-2	8,7	11,1	Fafonda irrigation ditch - upwards	Clear water No odour.	27/01/2021
AC-3	8,7	11,1	Canal irrigation ditch - upwards	Clear water No odour	27/01/2021
AC-4	8,86	11,2	Canal irrigation ditch - downwards	Clear water Organic/ faecal odour	27/01/2021

FIGURE 42. (LEFT) "FAFONDA IRRIGATION DITCH" (UPWARDS); (RIGHT) "CANAL IRRIGATION DITCH" (DOWNWARDS) SAMPLING POINTS (2021).

During the inspection of both surface watercourses, a similar water quality was observed upwards and downwards, but with apparently poorest quality for points located downwards, showing some organic-faecal odour. This aspect was associated to site wastewater flows from several farms consequently, not linked with the pilot construction.

Figure 43 shows the present sampling location.

FIGURE 43. SAMPLING POINTS LOCATION AT VILLAMAYOR. 2021 SAMPLING POINTS ARE OUTLINED.

Results

Water samples were analysed chemically for most environmentally significant compounds previously identified. These were analysed by TECNALIA (ENAC accredited lab). The analytical set applied was similar in all the samples: heavy metals (Al, Pb, Sb, As, Ba, Be, Tl, V), chlorides, sulphides, pH and electrical conductivity (gw and sw).

Results were compared with those obtained in the same location as in previous campaigns in 2018, and/or compared with regulatory references for the studied media, in order to determine the existence of any potential risk for human health and/or environment and evaluate the need for a specific risk assessment.

TABLE 14. ANALYTICAL SET AND METHODOLOGY

Compound	Method	Media
Aluminium (Al), Antimony (Sb), Arsenic (As), Barium (Ba), Beryllium (Be), Lead (Pb), Thallium (Tl), Vanadium (V)	ICP-OES	WATER
Chlorides	Ionic chromatography	
Sulphates		
Conductivity	Electrometric	
pH		

Groundwater (GW)

It was not possible to take a sample of groundwater in the latest 2021 sampling campaign, so, it is not possible to do a trend analysis for the monitoring period. Nevertheless, table 15 shows the latest samples taken in January 2020 on wells VG-P2 and VG-P3, and analytical results are contrasted with reference values.

TABLE 15. RESULTS (GW). COMPARATIVE CHART WITH REFERENCE VALUES.

Compound	VNGR ¹ (µg/L)	VGI ² (µg/L)	Directive 2006/118/EC (CHE) ³ (µg/L)	Endanger ed waters (CHE) ⁴ (µg/L)	VG-P2 (2020) (µg/L)	VG-P3 (2020) (µg/L)
Heavy metals						
Aluminium (Al)	-	-	-	200		
Antimony (Sb)	80	280	-	-	16	1,6
Arsenic (As)	50	70	10	-	2,1	16
Barium (Ba)	-	-	-	-	60	46
Beryllium (Be)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Lead (Pb)	-	-	10	-	6,1	29
Thallium (Tl)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Vanadium (V)	-	-	-	-	-	-
Copper (Cu)	-	-	-	2000	60	260
Chromium (total)	60	170		50	<0,005	<0,005
Mercury (Hg)	1	3	1		<0,000 5	<0,000 5
Molybdenum (Mo)	-	-	-	-	0,021	<0,02
Nickel (Ni)				20	<0,005	0,12
Cadmium (Cd)	20	60	5		<0,001	0,02
Cobalt (Co)					<0,02	<0,02
Zinc (Zn)					0,18	0,025
Anions						
Chlorides	-	-	10-8737 mg/L ⁽⁵⁾	-	425	118
Sulphates	-	-	27-4340 mg/L ⁽⁵⁾	-	1080	178
Fluorides	-	-	-	-	290	340

(1) VNGR – “Valor genérico de no riesgo (VNGR)” (No Risk Generic Value).

(2) VGI – “Valor genérico de intervención (VGI)” (Intervention Value)

(3) Reference DIRECTIVE 2006/118/EC for groundwater. Applicable to 71 endangered water masses.

(4) CHE reference values for endangered aquifers. Additional values to (4).

These following observations can be obtained for groundwater:

- Results were far below reference values, except for the Arsenic (As) for “Valor Umbral Directive 2006/118/EC (CHE)”. This value was compared, as a conservative exercise, with the CHE value for endangered waters, scenario that

in fact does not apply to the pilot site (sub-superficial waters are occasional and are not effectively connected to the deeper aquifer).

Evaluation:

- **No potential impact to groundwater (GW) derived from de pilot construction is observed.**

Surface water (SW)

Table 16 shows the results obtained for the sampled surface water. Results have been compared with a restrictive limit such as CHE values for drinkable water. In addition, sample AC-1 (2020) was included for comparison.

TABLE 16. SW ANALYTICAL RESULTS IN VILLAMAYOR

Compound (mg/L)	CHE (1) A1	AC-1 Fafonda downwards	AC-2 Fafonda upwards	AC-3 El Canal upwards	AC-4 El Canal downwards	AC-1 Fafonda downwards (2020)
Aluminium (Al)	-	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01	-
Antimony (Sb)	-	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001
Arsenic (As)	0,05	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001	<0,001
Barium (Ba)	0,1	<0,02	<0,02	<0,02	<0,02	<0,02
Beryllium (Be)	-	<0,02	<0,02	<0,02	<0,02	-
Lead (Pb)	0,05	<0,005	<0,005	<0,005	<0,005	<0,005
Thallium (Tl)	-	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01	<0,01	-
Vanadium (V)	-	<0,02	<0,02	<0,02	<0,02	-
Chlorides	200	31,9	31,8	31,8	31,8	15,6
Sulphates	250	105	105	105	105	32,4
Conductivity (µS/cm)	110 0	508	513	513	511	-
pH	6,5- 8,5	8,69	8,69	8,69	8,69	-
Temp (°C)	25	11,2	11,2	11,2	11,2	-

(1) Ref: council Directive 75/440/EEC of 16 June 1975 concerning the quality required of surface water intended for the abstraction of drinking water in the Member States) – Type A-1, simple treatment and disinfection. Reference for drinkable water quality (CHE).

From the analysis of Table 12 the following observations were done for Surface waters:

- Results are far below from reference values.
- Very similar chemical water qualities upwards and downwards to the pilot.
- Slight basic pH in all waters.
- Organic – fecal odor in two downward samples.

Evaluation:

- **No impact to the surface waters (SW) derived from the pilot construction is detected.**

3.4. Environmental monitoring. Laboratory data

The environmental monitoring at laboratory scale is based in the preparation of laboratory specimens at the same conditions as placed onsite with the same constituent elements taken from the worksite (WPFA, Soil and Cement). These specimens are preserved in a climatic chamber at 20°C for 360 days and leaching test are carried out at 7, 30, 60, 180 and 360 days. The following graphics show the results obtained for the different compounds of concern expecificed in the Royal Decree 646/2020 of 7th Luly regulating the landfilling criteria of wastes. The Inert category has been reflected in the dashed line in each graph.

Fluoride. The samples are below the limit for inert waste as shown in Figure 44. Although, in WPFA samples, it is higher than in the soil and soil with cement samples except for 360 days.

FIGURE 44: LEACHING TEST. FLUORIDE RELEASES FROM COMPLIANCE LEACHING TEST EVOLUTION.

Chloride. Only samples that were made by WPFA passed the limit for inert waste, however, it is below the limit for non-hazardous limit as shown in Figure 45.

FIGURE 45: LEACHING TEST. CHLORIDE RELEASES FROM COMPLIANCE LEACHING TEST EVOLUTION.

The **sulphate values** depend highly on the soil and the portion of the selected soil. Both WPFA and cement have a low sulphates content. The soil in 60, 180 and 360 days surpassed the limit value as shown in Figure 46 due to the naturally occurrence of sulphates in the local soils. In some cases, stabilized soil exceeds the sulphate limit, due to soil sampling variability.

FIGURE 46: LEACHING TEST. SULPHATE RELEASES FROM COMPLIANCE LEACHING TEST EVOLUTION.

The release of **heavy metals** showed a high amount of barium (Ba) in WPFA and cement surpassing both inert and non-hazardous value limits (Figure 47). Additionally, WPFA tends

to surpass the antimony (Sb), and cement surpassed the chromium (Cr). The soil used in stabilization and subgrade soil did not released any metal threshold value.

FIGURE 47: HEAVY METALS FOR RAW MATERIAL USED IN S-EST3.

The soil with curing does not undergo any changes in releasing heavy metals, and all the elements tend to stay nearly constant and below the limit value, except in antimony at 360 days (Figure 48).

FIGURE 48: HEAVY METALS FOR SOIL USED IN TRIAL AT DIFFERENT CURING TIME (TESTED AT THE SAME AGES AS STABILIZED SOIL).

Figure 49 shows the released of the elements of concern for different curing ages. At first, the amount of barium is high, but with stabilization dramatically reduces until staying clearly within the inert category. Barium gets quickly into carbonates and calcium silicate hydrates by partially replacing calcium with during the stabilisation process becoming quickly inert. The process is similar with lead. However, antimony is still above the inert limit and it seems that high pH conditions facilitates metal mobility.

FIGURE 49: HEAVY METALS FOR STABILIZED SOIL WITH 5% WPFA AT DIFFERENT CURING TIME.

The stabilized soil with cement at 360 days additional to zinc, copper and antimony surpassed the threshold limit for Inert Waste by a small margin (Figure 50).

FIGURE 50: HEAVY METALS FOR STABILIZED SOIL WITH 3% CEM IV AT DIFFERENT CURING TIME.

4. Soil – cement layer

The soils cement layer was executed in October 2019 in an active construction site, the A-31 A-33 highways connection. This situation conditions the monitoring, as the layer is encapsulated between sealing bituminous materials so that, environmental onsite monitoring did not make sense, but also the access to the site were not possible until the placement of the asphalt layer so that, the technical performance onsite monitoring were delayed for one year due to the construction restrictions. Consequently, monitoring of the soil cement layer has been mainly based on laboratory specimens.

4.1. Technical performance. Field data

The monitoring system employed along the soil – WPFA layer pilot was the Falling Weight Deflectometer (FWD).

The FWD is a non-destructive measurement tool used to determine the in-situ structural performance of an existing pavement structure. Its use is widely spread across the pavement design industry and it is used to:

- Identify areas of weak pavement
- Back-calculate layer properties for use in overlay designs
- Estimate the remaining life of the structure

For the aim of the project, only first premise applies since all measurements were taken 16 months after the pilot execution with no road traffic yet.

The process of the Falling Weight Deflectometer consists in applying a dynamic load to the pavement structure in the form of a standardised "drop weight" and measure the deflection at various points longitudinally in the pavement to recreate the "deflection bowl" of a wheel load.

This process is typically undertaken repetitiously so as to provide statistically validated deflections in order to develop 'homogenous' sections within the road and are correlated with the existing pavement compositions to identify the pavement performance.

The concept of identifying homogenous sections is used to characterise a road section by its characteristic performance and consequently determines a representative performance value.

FIGURE 51. FALLING WEIGHT DEFLECTOMETER USED AT LA FONT DE LA FIGUERA A-31 HIGHWAY

The device used was a PRIMAX 2500, which completely follows standard UNE 41250-3 "Test methods for measurement of pavement deflection. Part 3: Falling weight deflectometer". It consists of:

- A towing vehicle that allows the device to be moved to the place of measurement and that contains a computer and the command system. It is from there from where the operator performs the tests easily and simply.
- An electric system for lifting the test masses to a certain height (adjustable by the operator) from which they are dropped onto a test plate with a diameter of 30 cm. Depending on the applied mass and the chosen fall height, it is possible to choose the desired load and the appropriate load pulse duration.
- Geophones that are located: one under the load plate that measures the maximum deflection, and the others at variable distances from the point of impact. The measurements allow the definition of the deformation of the pavement.
- An odometer makes it possible to accurately measure the distance to the origin, in such a way that the test begins at a point with a known situation.

FWD tests took place on an asphalt mix layer located over a base layer of graded aggregate WPFA-stabilised and over graded aggregate cement-stabilised (pattern).

Table 17. FWD MEASUREMENT POINTS

Road section	Measurement direction	Initial km point	Final km point	Length
Asphalt mix + cement-stabilised layer (pattern)	Villena – La Encina	0+300	0+700	400 m
	La Encina - Villena	0+700	0+260	440 m
Asphalt mix + WPFA-stabilised layer	Villena – La Encina	0+800	1+160	360 m
	La Encina - Villena	1+180	0+820	360 m

Results

The average deflection above cement-stabilised GA in each stretch is 0.192 and 0.2275 mm respectively and over WPFA-stabilised layer is 0.116 and 0.134 mm. It seems that WPFA-stabilized material has a more rigid behaviour at the age at the tests were performed. However, its behaviour must be evaluated once the road traffic has acted on each section.

According to the Spanish Standard 6.3 IC: “*Rehabilitation of pavements*”, a road pavement is not susceptible to be evaluated in terms of its structural behaviour or possible rehabilitation when the maximum deflection in the LWD test is less than 0.40 mm (Chapter 9). This premise is fulfilled in all the cases evaluated.

Results are shown in the following tables and figures.

CEMENT-STABILISED GRADED AGGREGATE (PATTERN):

CLIENT: ACCIONA
ROAD: A-33
DATE: 22/02/2021

LAYER: **CEMENT-STABILISED GA**
STRETCH: VILLENA – LA ENCINA
INITIAL KM: 0+300
FINAL KM: 0+700

Humidity correction 1.15
Poisson ratio 0.35
Plate radius (mm) 150

DISTANCE	KM POINT	APPLIED PRESSURE	SURFACE MODULUS	CURVATURE RATIO	PAVEMENT TEMPERATURE	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 1)	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 2)	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 3)	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 4)	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 5)	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 6)	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 7)	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 8)	DEFLECTION (GEPHONE 9)	TEMPERATURE CORRECTION	MAXIMUM DEFLECTION
(m)	(m)	(Kpa)	(Mpa)	(m)	(°C)	(micras)		(10 ⁻² mm)								
0	0+300	903	1.505	1685	8,8	157,9	141,6	131,2	124,6	114,3	110,4	91,4	75,1	65,8	1,00	18
40	0+340	894	1.236	888	9,2	190,4	159	139,7	125,9	110,1	101,9	78,7	61,7	53,4	1,00	22
80	0+380	887	1.517	1233	9,2	153,9	130,3	117,4	108,5	96,8	90,6	70,6	53,6	46,1	1,00	18
120	0+420	925	1.846	1145	9,4	131,9	104,6	92,6	86,4	78	74,7	59,4	46,9	42,8	1,00	15
160	0+460	895	1.427	1049	9,2	165,1	138,3	122,2	111,8	99,6	93,2	73	56,7	50,9	1,00	19
200	0+500	890	1.317	918	9,2	177,9	146,5	128,9	117,9	105,5	99,3	79	63,6	55,4	1,00	21
240	0+540	882	1.063	667	8,9	218,5	175,2	151	134,7	117,3	107,5	80,7	62,1	54,2	1,00	26
280	0+580	883	1.346	1002	8,7	172,7	143,7	127,8	118	106,2	100,5	81,3	65,6	59,3	1,00	20
320	0+620	897	1.826	1114	8,7	129,3	102,3	88,9	80,6	70,5	65,7	49,8	38,1	35,3	1,00	15
360	0+660	880	1.580	1360	8,9	146,6	128,2	113,5	101,9	87,5	79,2	57,8	42,5	37,9	1,00	17
400	0+700	880	1.376	1372	9	168,3	149,3	135,5	124,8	110,4	101,8	75,9	54,8	44,8	1,00	20

CLIENT: ACCIONA
ROAD: A-33
DATE: 22/02/2021

LAYER: **CEMENT-STABILISED GA**
STRETCH: LA ENCINA – VILLENA
INITIAL KM: 0+700
FINAL KM: 0+260

Humidity correction 1.15
Poisson ratio 0.35
Plate radius (mm) 150

DISTANCE	KM POINT	APPLIED PRESSURE	SURFACE MODULUS	CURVATURE RATIO	PAVEMENT TEMPERATURE	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 1)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 2)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 3)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 4)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 5)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 6)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 7)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 8)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 9)	TEMP. CORR.	MAX. DEFL.
(m)	(m)	(Kpa)	(Mpa)	(m)	(°C)	(micras)		(mm)								
0	0+700	889	1.764	1069	8,7	132,7	105,3	90,6	80,8	69,5	64,4	48,4	36,4	31,3	1,00	15
40	0+660	902	1.204	1056	8,7	197,3	171,4	154,7	141,2	123,7	113,5	83,7	62,4	52,2	1,00	23
80	0+620	899	1.773	1420	8,9	133,5	111,5	101,8	95,3	86,4	82,4	66,5	52,9	47,6	1,00	15
120	0+580	881	639	335	8,9	36,3	276,9	228,8	194,5	161,9	142,1	104,6	81,3	72,4	1,00	43
160	0+540	886	1.054	608	8,6	221,2	174	147,2	129,3	111	100,4	76,4	59,7	53,1	1,00	26
200	0+500	891	1.354	798	8,8	173,2	135,8	116,8	105,1	92,7	86,3	68,4	55,1	50,2	1,00	20
240	0+460	902	1.238	667	9	191,8	146,8	124,3	110,4	95,9	88,3	67,7	53,4	49	1,00	22
280	0+420	912	1.475	787	9,1	162,8	124,9	105,6	93,9	81	74,2	56,3	43,6	39,6	1,00	19
320	0+380	892	1.182	731	8,8	198,7	159,6	137,1	120,9	103,2	92,6	67,2	49,4	42,2	1,00	23
360	0+340	884	1.048	705	8,9	222	181,6	158,2	141,4	122,5	110,6	81,4	60,1	49,6	1,00	26
400	0+300	908	1.436	976	8,9	166,4	135,4	120,3	110,8	98,8	92,3	72,5	56,8	50,2	1,00	19
440	0+260	897	1.270	827	8,7	186	149,3	131,6	119,6	106,2	98,4	76	59,3	52,3	1,00	22

WPFA-STABILISED GRADED AGGREGATE:

CLIENT: ACCIONA
ROAD: A-33
DATE: 22/02/2021

LAYER: **WPFA-STABILISED GA**
STRETCH: VILLENA – LA ENCINA
INITIAL KM: 0+800
FINAL KM: 1+160

Humidity correction: 1.15
Poisson ratio: 0.35
Plate radius (mm): 150

DISTANCE (m)	KM POINT (m)	APPLIED PRESSURE (Kpa)	SURFACE MODULUS (Mpa)	CURVATURE RATIO (m)	PAVEMENT TEMP. (°C)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 1) (micras)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 2) (micras)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 3) (micras)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 4) (micras)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 5) (micras)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 6) (micras)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 7) (micras)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 8) (micras)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 9) (micras)	TEMP. CORR.	MAX. DEF.
0	0+800	890	2.202	1692	11.4	106.4	88.1	79.8	74.5	66.1	61.0	44.9	33.1	28.3	1.00	12
40	0+840	918	2.557	2055	11.6	94.5	79.7	72.6	68.5	61.8	58.4	44.6	33.2	29.0	1.00	11
80	0+880	894	2.132	2045	11.3	110.4	95.3	88.4	84.4	77.8	75.4	61.5	46.1	38.8	1.00	13
120	0+920	920	2.497	1982	11.4	97.0	80.7	74.3	70.0	62.0	56.2	39.2	29.3	25.7	1.00	11
160	0+960	911	2.559	2261	11.3	93.7	79.5	73.8	70.8	65.4	62.7	51.3	40.7	36.1	1.00	11
200	1+000	899	3.781	2123	11.8	62.6	45.4	41.4	40.0	36.6	36.3	29.1	22.2	20.7	1.00	7
240	1+040	911	2.333	1475	11.1	102.8	81.0	72.3	67.1	60.3	57.4	45.0	33.7	28.6	1.00	12
280	1+080	902	2.230	2381	11.3	106.5	93.7	87.6	83.8	77.3	74.0	58.1	47.0	40.7	1.00	12
320	1+120	890	2.433	2778	10.4	96.3	85.4	80.1	77.8	72.6	70.7	59.6	49.1	44.6	1.00	11
360	1+160	870	1.693	1169	10.3	135.3	108.8	96.8	90.3	81.7	77.9	62.9	49.4	43.6	1.00	16

CLIENT: ACCIONA
ROAD: A-33
DATE: 22/02/2021

LAYER: **WPFA-STABILISED GA**
STRETCH: LA ENCINA – VILLENA
INITIAL KM: 1+180
FINAL KM: 0+820

Humidity correction 1.15
Poisson ratio 0.35
Plate radius (mm) 150

DISTANCE	KM POINT	APPLIED PRESSURE	SURFACE MODULUS	CURVATURE RATIO	PAVEMENT TEMPERATURE	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 1)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 2)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 3)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 4)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 5)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 6)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 7)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 8)	DEFLECTION (GEOPHONE 9)	TEMP. CORR.	MAXIMUM DEFLECTION
(m)	(m)	(Kpa)	(Mpa)	(m)	(°C)	(micras)		[10 ⁻² mm]								
0	1+180	901	1.584	1293	8.4	149.7	127.4	114.9	105.7	92.8	85.8	63.8	46.5	38.8	1.00	17
40	1+140	922	1.013	704	8.6	239.6	197.1	175.7	158.9	137.8	124.8	89.2	63.0	50.3	1.00	27
80	1+100	896	1.935	2514	8.7	121.9	110.1	104.0	100.4	92.1	89.0	72.8	56.8	48.9	1.00	14
120	1+060	912	2.430	2000	9.1	98.8	82.7	76.3	73.0	66.6	64.7	53.0	42.2	38.3	1.00	11
160	1+020	910	3.242	2153	9.3	73.9	58.9	53.0	50.2	45.0	43.4	33.2	23.4	21.0	1.00	8
200	0+980	906	2.669	1312	9.2	89.7	65.3	56.4	49.8	42.7	40.0	29.6	21.8	20.4	1.00	10
240	0+940	916	2.546	1698	9.3	94.7	76.3	68.2	64.2	57.7	56.2	43.9	33.1	29.7	1.00	11
280	0+900	913	2.445	1907	9.4	96.3	81.5	74.7	70.2	63.7	61.3	50.5	39.6	35.2	1.00	11
320	0+860	900	2.341	1286	9.6	101.2	76.1	66.2	61.3	53.7	51.1	39.3	29.6	26.6	1.00	12
360	0+820	918	2.129	1822	9.7	113.5	96.5	88.8	83.7	75.4	71.3	53.5	37.1	31.1	1.00	13

4.2. Technical performance. Laboratory data

This section is dedicated to stabilizing a soil with WPFA in order to reach the Soil-Cement category recognised by Spanish Regulation for bridges and roads (PG3). According to Spanish guidelines for roads and bridges, a Soil-Cement needs to have a strength between 2.5 and 4.5 MPa at seven days.

To carry out the experiments firstly, it is necessary to characterize the raw material. A profound characterization of soil was carried out which includes the Los Angeles (L.A.) Abrasion (EN 1097-2), Flakiness index (EN 933-3), particle size distribution, Atterberg limits, sand equivalent test (EN 933-8), chemical composition, Total sulphates, total sulphur and organic matter content (OM). To characterize the WPFA, chemical, mineralogical properties and loss on ignition was carried out.

After determining the properties of raw material, the study continued with stabilizing the soil with 5.2 wt% of WPFA. In order to determine the density and the optimum water content (OW), the proctor test was carried out according to European standard (UNE 103501) with adding 5.2 wt% to the soil. From the previous studies on WPFA, a 30 minutes delay time was added to the mix after adding the water.

The compressive strength test according to European standard (EN 13286-41) was carried out with OW and the obtained density. Four samples for different ages were fabricated. The samples were placed in a chamber room with 95% relative humidity to cure for 7, 30, 60, 180 and 360 days. After designated age, the sample was weighted, and the compressive strength was carried out. To have a control, samples were made using 3 wt% cement and cured for different ages.

The **particle size distribution** of soil is found in Figure 52. The differentiate the soil from previous soil, it is called Soil-Cement. The soil is characterized as A-1-a according to AASHTO, and GM-GP, poorly graded according to unified soil classification system. However, it complies with requirement mentioned in PG3 (Figure 52).

FIGURE 52: SOIL PARTICLE SIZE DISTRIBUTION AND ITS LIMIT ACCORDING TO PG3.

Its LA coefficient according to Standard should be between 30-40 % for sieve size 10-12.5 mm and 60-70% for sieve 12.5-14 mm. the result obtained 35% for sieve size 10-12.5 mm and 64 % for 12.5-14 mm. the LA coefficient was 29. The sand equivalent test was obtained 55%. The flakiness index was obtained 0.0014 %, which is less than 1%. For carrying out the total sulphates, total sulphur and organic matter content, the soil was divided into two fractions. Fine fraction, which corresponds to the fraction smaller than 4mm, while coarse fraction, which is a representative, sample of the complete material. The test is carried out on the two fractions in order to verify if there are variation of the amounts of sulphates in the fine or coarse fraction of the material.

As shown in Table 18, the results obtained from the soil samples meet the requirements established in PG3.

TABLE 18: PROPERTIES OF SOIL.

Soil	Total sulphates (<1%)	Total Sulphur	OM content	Requirement of PG3
Fine fraction	0.24%	0.28%	0.9	Comply
Coarse fraction	0.25%	0.29%	n.m.	Comply

In Table 19, the results obtained from Atterberg limits was demonstrated where it was determined that the material did not contain a plastic limit or a liquid limit. The results meet the requirements established by PG 3.

TABLE 19: ATTERBERG LIMITS OF SOIL.

	<i>Result</i>	<i>Standard PG 3</i>
Liquid limit	NA	Comply
Plastic limit	NA	Comply
Plasticity index	NA	Comply

WPA has as main chemical element (CaO) with 52.7%, followed by (SiO₂) with 12.18% and (Al₂O₃) 7.67%. The loss on ignition obtained 18.80%. The main elements of cement IV are (CaO) with 35.33%, followed by (SiO₂) with 38.11% and (Al₂O₃) with 10.9%. Loss on ignition was obtained 2.5%.

TABLE 20: CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF RAW MATERIAL (SOIL CEMENT).

<i>Element</i>	<i>Soil (wt%)</i>	<i>WPA (wt%)</i>	<i>Cement IV (wt%)</i>
CaO	36.51	52.69	35.33
SiO₂	2.53	12.18	38.11
MgO	15.26	1.61	1.51
Al₂O₃	-	7.67	10.9
SO₃	0.25	1.71	2.61
K₂O	0.23	0.41	1.66
Fe₂O₃	0.21	1.24	5.59
Na₂O	0.15	0.52	0.56
Others	0.33	3.15	1.07
Lol	44.51	18.80	2.5
Free Lime Content		11.56	

In WPA, the minerals are portlandite, calcite, lime, calcium silicate, gehlenite, and aluminium (Figure 53). The minerals of cement are calcium silicate, silicon, brownmillerite, tricalcium aluminium, and gypsum (Figure 54). The soil contains dolomite, calcite and quartz (Figure 55). The free lime test was performed on a WPA ash sample and its content is 11.56%. The free lime can lead to expansions in soil samples. To avoid this, a 30 minutes delay time was added to samples after mixing with water.

FIGURE 53: WPFA DIFFRACTOGRAM.

FIGURE 54: CEMENT IV/B (Q) 32.5N DIFFRACTOGRAM.

FIGURE 55: SOIL DIFFRACTOGRAM.

The modified proctor test was carried out to determine the dry density and the optimum moisture content. For carrying out the proctor test with WPFA, 30 minutes delay time was added to avoid possible expansion due to existence of quicklime. The density with soil + 5.2 %wt WPFA obtained 2.13 g/cm³, and for soil + 3 %wt cement was obtained 2.26 g/cm³ (Figure 56).

FIGURE 56: PROCTOR TEST.

After defining the density and the moisture content, samples were made for compressive strength for 7, 28, 90, 180 and 360 days. Immediately after fabricating the samples, they were placed inside chamber room with a temperature of 20 °C and 95 % relative humidity.

The obtained results are shown in

Figure 577. At 7 days, soil + WPFA gained 2.5 MPa, and soil + cement gained 3.63 MPa. Stabilization with both WPFA and cement complies with PG3 requirement that is 2.5 MPa at 7 days. The strength for WPFA samples improved by 26 % at 28 days, from 28 to 90 days, 22% %, and from 90 days to 180 days, 4 %, reaching 4.5 MPa. However, from 180 days to 360 days, no improvement was observed. For cement samples, the strength from 7 to 28 days improved by 19 %, from 28 to 90 days, improved by 22 %, and for 180 and 360 days, by 19 and 1 %, respectively.

FIGURE 57: COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH FOR SOIL-WPFA (RIGHT) AND CEMENT-SOIL LAYER (LEFT).

4.3. Environmental laboratory monitoring

The leaching properties of WPFA, cement and soil and the correspondant blends made with soil + 5.2 %wt WPFA, and soil + 3 %wt cement have been characterised. The blends were prepared at the same worksite conditions (same density and moisture content) and cured for different ages to see the whether the elements of concern can be immobilized. Both WPFA and soil are highly alkaline and conductive (Figure 58 and Figure 59). The pH of soil was 9.25 and the stabilised soil reached 12.8. The pH lowered after curing however, still maintaining the highly alkiline nature. The conductivity lowered more clearly, as shown in figure 59.

FIGURE 58: PH OF RAW AND CURED SOIL + BINDER.

FIGURE 59: CONDUCTIVITY OF RAW AND CURED SOIL + BINDER.

Figure 60 shows the amount of fluoride of raw WPFA and raw cement, then with soil stabilization at different ages. For all ages, both for soil + WPFA and soil + cement, the release of fluoride is below the inert waste threshold limit.

FIGURE 60: FLUORIDE RELEASE OF SOIL + 5.2% WPFA AND SOIL + 3% CEMENT.

Figure 61 shows the amount of chloride release of raw WPFA and raw cement, then with soil stabilization at different ages. The raw WPFA released around 10,000 mg/kg, but still being within the non-hazardous category. Adding WPFA to soil, decreased the chloride leaching up to 828 mg/kg and 1051 mg/kg respectively, decreasing close to the inert waste category. At 30, 180 and 360 days, the values are lower than inert waste category threshold limit. All of the cement values for chloride are less than 800 mg/kg (Figure 61).

FIGURE 61: CHLORIDE RELEASE OF SOIL + 5.2% WPFA AND SOIL + 3% CEMENT.

As shown in Figure 62, all the values for sulphate are below the inert waste category. It must be highlighted that the sulphate values depend highly on soil and its particle distribution.

FIGURE 62: SULFATE RELEASE OF SOIL + 5.2% WPFA AND SOIL + 3% CEMENT.

As shown in Figure 63, the lead (Pb) barium (Ba) values in WPFA surpassed both inert waste and non-hazardous waste values however, after blending the values keep clearly below the inert category limit. Only antimony surpassed the inert waste limit after blending.

Figure 64 shows the heavy metal release in cement raw and blends of soil + 3% cement. Initially (cement raw), all the values remained within the inert waste category except for antimony. After blending with soil, the leaching values are similar and do not show clear variations along the curing time. Just Nickel (Ni) showed punctually a value above the inert waste threshold limit and Antinomy remained above this level.

FIGURE 63: HEAVY METAL RELEASE OF SOIL + 5.2% WPFA.

FIGURE 64: HEAVY METAL RELEASE OF SOIL + 3% CEMENT.

Conclusion

With adding 5.2% WPFA to the soil, it is possible to stabilize it and reach the minimum requirement of PG3 (2.5 MPa at 7 days for the Soil-Cement layer mentioned in PG3.

From the leaching point of view, WPFA is considered a non-hazardous material however, after blending with soil, the mobility of the elements of concern in the final product decreased until reaching the inert waste category in all parameters except for Antimony and chlorides anyway, these values kept close to the inert category.

5. Conclusions

Three pilots have been built corresponding with the three stabilised soil layers recognised by the Spanish Road Regulation. An intensive monitoring programme has been followed for the last 3 years in order to assess the mechanical (technical) and environmental performance based on onsite long-term monitoring. Field data has been complemented with laboratory testing by means of producing specimens under worksite placement conditions to determine leaching properties and mechanical evolution at delayed curing conditions.

S-EST2-type layer monitoring has been systematically inspected showing a perfect state of repair. There is a great difference with the same road not included in the pilot, where the state is much poorer. The load plate tests conducted after two years indicated that the static modulus decreased in one of the tests although keeping the same formation level category. The contrast stretch made of lime increased the static modulus, although maintaining the formation level category as well.

From the environmental point of view, there were intense field sampling and testing in order to identify any increased level of elements of concern in the surroundings (vegetation, sediments and groundwater recovered from beneath the road axis). The analysis showed that all salts such as chlorides and sulfates lowered concentrations, meanwhile heavy metals increased concentrations in soils, although much below the threshold limits for potential risk. No impact was observed in groundwater. Vegetation showed no increased in metals and leaching water values were far below the most conservative standards, where barium showed a noticeable increase of 56%, but it must be considered that soils concentration in this compound are far below reference values for soils in the site. The environmental assessment resulted in "no risk for the people or the environment"

The laboratory leaching tests showed that all the values complied with the inert waste category except for chlorides, due to the nature of the local soil, enriched in chlorides. Antimony naturally occurring in the soil seems to leach under high pH surpassing the inert category but clearly remaining within the non-hazardous category.

S-EST3-type layer monitoring was inspected at the same time as the former pilot. The status of repair was excellent as well, with some damages detected (and repaired) during the inspections but not related with the stabilised layer performance. Some cracking was observed in the cement contrast stretch related with shrinkage due to the high rigidity deployed by cement. No cracking or swell detected in the WPPFA stretched for the last three years. The load plate tests conducted in the same mileages as done just after the pilot building showed that the WPPFA increased the static modulus by a 17 % and the cement stretch (one single point) decreased by 50 %, which can be considered not representative. The compressive strength evolution indicates that WPPFA raised the

maximum strength at 60 days and then remained constant while cement kept growing by 50 % from 28 days to 360.

A complete laboratory analysis was conducted to evaluate swelling due to ettringite formation in both cement and WPFA stabilised samples by immersion in different sulfate solutions. The maximum swell measured was lower than 2 % at 770 days for the most challenging conditions. In general, the samples tend to shrink, being 0.32 % of maximum shrinkage measured.

The environmental monitoring showed similar results as for S-EST2 layer. Surficial waters did not show any compositional difference upstream and downstream the pilot so no impact has been observed as a consequence of the WPFA stabilisation in a three years scenario. After several attempts, it was not possible to obtain representative groundwater from the existing wells, that tried to catch sub-superficial water levels -notice that permanent aquifer is below 60-70 m.b.g. in the site.

The laboratory leaching tests showed no metal mobility as a consequence of the WPFA stabilisation except for Antimony that surpassed the Inert waste category however, the standard cement-stabilisation specimens showed the same Antimony leaching, interpreted as a mobilisation of the naturally occurring Antimony in soils as a consequence of the high pH typically required for soil stabilisation. In any case, the values remained in all cases within the Non-hazardous category. The rest of values remained within the inert category except for some minimal excess in the cement-stabilised soil at 360 days for Copper and Zinc.

Chlorides surpassed the inert waste category limit in the WPFA stabilised layer and occasionally, sulfates too in both WPFA and cement stabilised samples, due to the sulfate content of the natural soil.

The **soil-cement layer** was monitored through Falling Weight Deflectometer along the stretch and the contrast (cement-stabilised layer). The results showed that the WPFA-layer deflections were on average, 60 % lower than the cement-layer, implying more rigidity and less deformation than the equivalent cement-stretch.

The compressive strength evolution showed that the WPFA-Soil remained constant around 4.5 Mpa after 100 curing days whereas cement-stabilised samples increased the value until 7.5 Mpa at 200 days to remain constant afterwards.

The leaching properties showed the same trend as in the former pilots. Initial high Barium and Lead mobility in WPFA raw material quickly become inert when mixed and hydrated to form the stabilised material. On the contrary, Antimony shows certain leaching capacity at high pH surpassing the inert waste category in both cement and WPFA. Occasionally, cement stabilised soil showed certain Nickel mobility.

In conclusion, WPFA has demonstrated its hability as hydraulic road binder, complying with all technical requirements established in the Spanish Road Regulations. All pilots has shown a good technical performance after 3 years and no environmental impacts have been identified, showing a similar trend in metal mobility to other conventional stabilisations.

6. References

Internal sources

Paperchain Deliverables:

Deliverable 2.1: Baseline Reporte – PPI waste streams valorisation potential.

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Deliverable 4.1: Report on solutions feasibility and constraints.

Deliverable 5.3: Implementation of Circular Case 2. Road Applications

Deliverable 8.1: Report on transition assessment for circular economy processes.

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Directive 2006/118/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the protection of groundwater against pollution and deterioration

EN-12457-2 Characterisation of waste - Leaching - Compliance test for leaching of granular waste materials and sludges - Part 2: One stage batch test at a liquid to solid ratio of 10 l/kg for materials with particle size below 4 mm (without or with size reduction)

EN 13286-49 Unbound and hydraulically bound mixtures - Part 49: Accelerated swelling test for soil treated by lime and/or hydraulic binder

EN 13286-41 Unbound and hydraulically bound mixtures - Part 41: Test method for the determination of the compressive strength of hydraulically bound mixtures

EN 1097-2 Tests for mechanical and physical properties of aggregates - Part 2: Methods for the determination of resistance to fragmentation

EN 933-3 Tests for geometrical properties of aggregates - Part 3: Determination of particle shape - Flakiness index

EN 933-8 Tests for geometrical properties of aggregates - Part 8: Assessment of fines - Sand equivalent test

EN 103501 Geotechnic. Compaction test. Modified proctor.

Orden FOM/3459/2003, de 28 de noviembre, por la que se aprueba la norma 6.3-IC: "Rehabilitación de firmes", de la Instrucción de carreteras. 6.3 IC: "*Rehabilitation of pavements*".

PG3. Pliego de Prescripciones Técnicas para Obras de Carreteras y Puentes. Spanish Regulation for bridges and roads

Real Decreto 646/2020 de 7 de julio, por el que se regula la eliminación de residuos mediante depósito en vertedero